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LEXICAL STYLISTIC DEVICES

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ANNOTATION

The level of study and meaning of lexical literary devices are presented in the given article. Essential aspects of lexical tools and information about various research methods and their study will be discussed.

Terms belonging to the lexical level of the language and analyzes of lexical devices given by a number of terminological dictionaries and literary sources will be explained in the article.

In this article, we would like to mention different approaches to the study of literary terminology of figurative language, more specifically lexical stylistic devices.

There are many types of figurative language, including literary devices such as similes, metaphors, personification, and many others.

Key words: metaphor, metonymy, perspective, limitation, epithet, contiguity, context.

MAIN STYLISTIC DEVICES

Metaphor is the transfer of the name of one thing to another on the basis of the similarities and similarities of two things.

Metaphor has no formal limitations: it can be a word, a sentence, any part of a sentence or the whole, even part of the text or the entire text (Алиса в стране чудес).

Metaphors can only exist within a context.

Metaphors bring the reader to the surface to gain a new perspective on things.

The main function is to create images.

Example: England has two eyes: Oxford & Cambridge.

Style metaphors can be classified semantically and structurally.

Semantically: In true metaphor, the conflict between two meanings results in something of an Imaginery.

Real metaphors are found in emotional poetry and prose.

In a misleading metaphor, this is perceived vaguely.

For example, a chair leg, a ray of hope.

Misleading metaphors used in articles.

Structurally metaphors can be classified as simple (realized in one word and creating one image) and sustained (realized in a number of a logically connected words sentences) Metaphor may be based on similarity: Appearance or form – nut – орех, голова.

Temperature – boiling hot – кипяток, вспыльчивый характер.

Similarity of color – violet – фиолетовый, фиалка.

Similarity of function of use – hand – рука, стрелка часов.

The names of animals – ass – осёл, упрямый, глупый.

Metonymy is the transfer of meaning based on contiguity.

Metonymy is based on possible types of association:

1. part for the whole (a flight of fifty sails).
2. symbol for symbolic object (baldhead).
3. barrel instead of container (whole room applauds).
4. the material for the thing made of (glasses).
5. the author for his work.
6. the instrument for the agent of the action performed (his pen knows no compromise).

Metonymy is expressed by nouns.

Epithet expresses a characteristic of an object existing or imaginary. It's basic feature is emotiveness and subjectivity: the characteristic attached to the object to qualify it is always chosen by the speaker himself.

Thus epithet is based on interplay of logical and emotive meaning. The later is born in context & prevails over the logical meaning. Logical attributes (which are not stylistic devices) are objective and non-evaluative.

E.g.: a pretty young girl – logical attribute, a care and radiant maiden - epithet.

Epithets can be classified semantically (cold-blooded murder) and structurally (a lip sticky smile). Richard the Lion Heart.

SUMMARY COMPLETION: Stylistic devices are important in both writing and speaking because they add originality to your writing by providing clarity, emphasis, and freshness of expression. Reading a text with well-arranged stylistic devices is more enjoyable than reading a simple text.

The lexical elements of style are expressed at the word level, and variations in style may arise from the addition, deletion, or substitution of words.

These variations can result in a text that is often different in feeling, form, excitement.

When measuring the quality of written text, especially academic writing, lexical features are as important as grammatical features and should not be ignored.

The highly computational nature of vocabularies can make them good criteria for determining and measuring text quality.

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